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**An Analytical Model For Interlaminar Friction Prediction In
Prepreg Composite**

D. Mocerino, D. Aveiga, C. Gonzalez

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Outline

- Thermoforming, defects and friction
- Pull-out Test and Tests Results
- Interlaminar Contact Surface Examination
- Analytical Model ad Lubrication Theory
- Results
- Conclusion

Thermoforming
Manufacturing *

AS4/8552 PREPREG COMPOSITE

- Solid and viscous behaviour
- Temperature sensitivity

*Guzman-Maldonado, E., Hamila, N., Naouar, N., Moulin, G., & Boisse, P. (2016). Simulation of thermoplastic prepreg thermoforming based on a visco-hyperelastic model and a thermal homogenization. *Materials and Design*, 93 (January 2016).

- In the process of thermoforming, it can be observed that individual lamina within a given laminate undergoes varying degrees of deformation.
- Frictional resistance exists between the layers.
- Stress concentrations may arise due to the incapacity of certain areas of the lamina to undergo deformation.
- The formation of wrinkles occurs in areas where the primary stress is compressive.
- Following the application of a distributed pressure, the initial visible appearance is the occurrence of out-of-plane fibre waviness, followed by the formation of in-plane wrinkles.

*K. Cinar, N. Ersoy, Effect of fibre wrinkling to the spring-in behaviour of L-shaped composite materials, Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 69 (October)(2015) 105–114.

Interlaminar Shear Characterisation

Friction Test:

Variables

Temperature (°C)	40, 60
Pressure (bar)	0.5, 1, 2
Velocity (mm/min)	1, 3, 5, 10

Calculations

$$\mu = \frac{N_2}{2N_1}$$

Interlaminar Shear Characterisation

Friction Test: Is there a difference between ply-ply friction and ply-tool friction?

Ply-Tool

Ply-Ply

PLY-TOOL

PLY-PLY

PLY-TOOL

Clamping Pressure (bar)	Pulling velocity (mm/min)	Friction coefficients at 40°C Ply-Tool	Friction coefficients at 60°C Ply-Tool
0.5	1	0.47 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.03
	3	0.68 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.02
	5	0.78 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.008
	10	0.86 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.01
1	1	0.30 ± 0.02	0.10 ± 0.008
	3	0.42 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.007
	5	0.44 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.008
	10	0.55 ± 0.06	0.18 ± 0.005
2	1	0.21 ± 0.006	0.07 ± 0.007
	3	0.33 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.007
	5	0.35 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.008
	10	0.47 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.005

PLY-PLY

Clamping Pressure (bar)	Pulling velocity (mm/min)	Friction coefficients at 40°C Ply-Ply	Friction coefficients at 60°C Ply-Ply
0.5	1	0.59 ± 0.03	0.1 ± 0.004
	3	1.08 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.01
	5	1.23 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.005
	10	1.31 ± 0.07	0.3 ± 0.03
1	1	0.33 ± 0.007	0.09 ± 0.007
	3	0.67 ± 0.04	0.15 ± 0.001
	5	0.85 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.009
	10	1.27 ± 0.03	0.26 ± 0.02
2	1	0.23 ± 0.03	0.06 ± 0.003
	3	0.41 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.008
	5	0.54 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.01
	10	0.85 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.01

Roughness & Resin Layer

Composite Friction Surface

Contact type	40°C	60°C
Prepreg-prepreg	3.22 ± 0.23	3.17 ± 0.66
Prepreg-tool	3.93 ± 0.46	3.10 ± 0.12

$$H = \frac{\eta \dot{U}}{P}$$

H = Hersey Number
 η = Viscosity (Pa.s)
 \dot{U} = Velocity (s^{-1})
 P = Pressure (Pa)

$$\eta(T) = Ae^{\frac{-B}{RT}}$$

$A = 2.06548437 \times 10^{-9}$
 $B = 7.9498278 \times 10^4$
 R = Gas constant
 T = Temperature (K)

$$y^+(x) = \frac{h_0}{2} + A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right)$$

$$y^-(x) = -\frac{h_0}{2} - A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L} + \delta\right)$$

$$h(x) = h_0 + 2A_0 \cos \delta \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L} + \delta\right)$$

$$\tau_r(\hat{x}) = \eta \frac{\dot{U}}{2} + \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial \hat{x}}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{x}} \left(\frac{h^3}{\eta} \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial \hat{x}} \right) = 6\dot{U} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \hat{x}}$$

$$\mu = \frac{\bar{\tau}_r}{\bar{p}_r}$$

Estimated with optical images

Estimated with roughness

L = wavelength

A = wave amplitude

$\frac{h}{2}$ = half of total thickness of resin layer

Used Material AS4/8552

$L \approx 64 \mu\text{m}$

$A \approx 3.5 \mu\text{m}$

$h_0 = [3 - 15 \mu\text{m}]$

Friction Prediction

Used Material AS4/8552

$L \approx 64 \mu\text{m}$
 $A \approx 3.5 \mu\text{m}$
 $h_0 = [3 - 15 \mu\text{m}]$

Parametric Study

- Elevated temperatures have the potential to reduce the viscosity of the resin, leading to a notable decrease in the friction coefficient by a factor of 6 to 10. When high pressure is taken into consideration, the coefficient may decrease by a factor ranging from 15 to 18 times its original value.
- In general, it was observed that the Ply-Ply configuration exhibited higher friction values due to the presence of two additional layers of adhesive prepreg. Nevertheless, the frictional resistance exhibited identical behaviour as observed in the previous scenario.
- The examination of the prepreg surface after friction has revealed certain geometric characteristics such as resin accumulations, exposed fibres, and surface roughness. The phenomenon can be represented by a sinusoidal shape characterised by a specific wavelength and roughness.
- An analytical model was formulated. Using the wavelength and amplitude of the resin accumulations on the prepreg surface as inputs, a reliable friction coefficient can be determined.
- By comparison of the model and experimental results, a minimal deviation is detected in the prepreg-prepreg interaction at higher Hershey values. The observed outcome was postulated to be a result of dry lubrication, which can be attributed to the prevailing solid-to-fluid behaviour of the resin

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Prof. Carlos González

David Aveiga

Thanks for your attention

Any questions?

